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Spike-driven threshold-based learning with memristive synapses and neuromorphic silicon neurons

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Supplementary Information

S1. System setup

Figure S1 shows a photograph (Figure S1a) and the schematic (Figure S1b) of the experimental setup.

The neuromorphic chip is operated with the use of mainly three components:

- The Breakout Board supplies power (3.3 V) to the chip.
- The digital-to-analogue (DAC) board supplies bias-voltages to the chip in order to provide the integrated circuits with parameters such as firing-thresholds and time-constants which are represented as gate-voltages in the circuits. The DAC board is interfaced directly through USB.
- The FPGA-Board establishes digital communication. Here a Cypress Fx2 module provides a second USB interface to PC. Via this connection, monitor- and stimulus- commands are transmitted to the chip and firing activity in the form of address-events is received from it.
- The switch board allows protected switch of the device between the neuromorphic chip and the automatic test equipment (ATE) used to carry out DC operations and to read the device resistance.

In order to allow a convenient and easy use of the setup, a graphical user interface communicates both with the DAC board and the FPGA through the two USB interfaces and a layer of low-level drivers written in C-Programming language. From this single environment, amplitudes and duration of the programming protocol for performing operations on memristive devices, as well as the neurons parameters can be adjusted. External stimulation of the analogue sub-threshold neuron circuits can be performed for testing purposes by specifying the neuron to be stimulated, the frequency and the duration of the stimulus.

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Figure S1: (a) Photograph and (b) schematic of the experimental setup. (b) Insets: micro-photograph of the memristive devices (round inset, top left) and micro-graph of the neuromorphic die (square inset, bottom right).

S2. Switch PCB to interface neurons and synapses

Some operations like forming, DC programming to set the memristive device to a well-defined resistance state, and reading the resistance state of the device must be carried out with an ATE. However, the initial operating voltage at the memristive device terminals when using the ATE has to be 0 V, whereas the neuromorphic chip applies a voltage of 1.65 V to both the device terminals. The manual switch of the device between the two elements is therefore impossible because of electrostatic discharge which can cause severe damage to the memristive device. A custom PCB is then designed and fabricated to interface the memristive device both to the neuromorphic chip and to the ATE.

The board schematic is shown in Figure S2a. The memristive device under test (DUT) can be connected to the ATE or to the neuromorphic chip through two Double Pole Single Throw reed relays ($DPST_3$ and $DPST_2$, respectively). Due to the different initial operating voltages of the ATE (0 V) and of the neuromorphic chip (1.65 V), there cannot be a direct commutation between the two elements, but the voltage at the DUT terminals has to be slowly driven from 0 V to 1.65 V and back. Therefore, the low-pass passive filter R_1C_1 (time constant $\tau = 10$ ms) is added as intermediate stage of the commutation. The Single Pole Double Throw reed relay $SPDT_1$ drives the voltage across C_1 , which is applied to the DUT through the reed relay $DPST_1$, to either 1.65 V or 0 V. All the relays are controlled via software by the digital input / output ports of the ATE.

Figures S2b and S2c show the voltage at DUT terminals and the voltage drop across the DUT (top panel: voltage at top electrode; middle panel: voltage at bottom electrode; bottom panel: voltage drop across the DUT) when commuting from the ATE to the neuromorphic chip (see Figure S2b) and back (see Figure S2c). As shown in the bottom panels of the two plots, during the commutation the overall voltage across the DUT is always kept within ± 0.2 V, which is a safe voltage and does not affect the device resistance.

When alternating from the ATE to the neuromorphic chip, the DUT is initially connected to the ATE through $DPST_3$. Then, the DUT is connected to the passive filter, whose output voltage across C_1 is initially 0 V. $SPDT_1$ transitions to 1.65 V and the voltage at DUT terminals rises to 1.65 V, as shown

in Figure S2b. Once the transient is over, the DUT is connected to the neuromorphic chip. The dual procedure is adopted for the reverse commutation (see Figure S2c).

Figure S2: (a) Schematic of the board interfacing the memristive device (DUT) with the ATE and the neuromorphic chip. (b)-(c) Commutation of the DUT from the ATE to the neuromorphic chip (b) and back (c). In both figures, top panel shows the voltage at DUT top electrode ($NE1_{out}$), middle panel the voltage at DUT bottom electrode ($NE2_{in}$), and bottom panel the voltage drop across the memristive synapse (ΔV).

S3. Description of CMOS neurons

A detailed description of neuron and plasticity circuits used can be found in [1], whereas the detailed description of pre- and post- interfaces can be found in [2]. In the following, we summarise the neuron model, referring to the schematic in Figure S3. Since the neuron model is conceived to closely reproduce the behaviour of biological neurons, we refer to the biological channels and ions intervening in the generation of a biological action potential.

The core element of the neuron architecture is a capacitor (C_{mem}) whose voltage (V_{mem}) resembles the membrane potential. The capacitor is initially discharged. When a stimulus arrives from the pre-synaptic neuron, the resulting excitatory post-synaptic current (EPSC, I_{syn} in the Figure) is integrated and C_{mem} is charged. A circuit emulating the Cl^- channels constantly discharges C_{mem} (leak function), but the co-appearance of several EPSCs contribute to increase V_{mem} above a threshold (namely, the firing threshold). As soon as the firing threshold is overcome, a circuit block emulating biological Na^+ channels activates and generates an action potential. By this mechanism, V_{mem} further increases rapidly, until a circuit block emulating biological K^+ channel dynamics discharges C_{mem} , and resets the membrane potential. Now, V_{mem} is reset to the resting potential and capable of firing again, after the passing of a refractory period.

In addition to the neuron model, a plasticity circuit block compare the state of the membrane potential and the level of the Ca^{2+} concentration to some thresholds. The levels of membrane potential and Calcium variable with respect to the thresholds determine the plasticity operation of the neuron, i.e. potentiation (LTP), depression (LTD), or none (neutral). The thresholds are set externally, as described in the main body of the manuscript (see Section 3.3).

Figure S3: High-level schematic of the CMOS neuron.

Regarding circuit architecture, a differential pair integrator (DPI), as described in [3], models the neuron's leak conductance due to Cl^- channels. The Calcium variable is implemented with a DPI as well, whereas the comparisons with the thresholds are implemented through three winner-take-all (WTA) networks, which use current conveyors as described in [4]. Signal */spike* is a digital signal used for digital communication of spikes and it is active whenever a spike is sensed.

To interface the neuron with the memristive synapse, two circuits were designed, namely pre-interface circuit and post-interface circuit. The first one uses two pulse extenders and one bit digit to generate a bi-phasic pulse whenever an action potential is generated. The second one, instead, uses two pulse extenders, a digital memoryless control block, two comparators and two operational amplifier implementing an active clamp technique to generate a potentiation, depression, or neutral pulse and to read the current from the synapse. Please note that the voltage of the read phase is positive when following a depressing spike, whereas it is negative when preceding a potentiating spike. Therefore, the negative read pulse is mirrored internally so that the DPI circuit carrying out the integration and filtering of the current from the memristive synapse can do it regardless the pulse polarity.

References

- [1] Qiao et al. (2015), *Front. Neurosci.*, 9:141
- [2] Mostafa et al. (2016), *Proc. IEEE ISCAS*, 926
- [3] Bartolozzi and Indiveri, *Neural Comput.* 19, 2581-2603 (2007)
- [4] Liu et al. *Analog VLSI: Circuits and Principles*, MIT Press (2002)